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Depression: nature, definition, clinical presentation, outcome

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Abstract

Introduction : Currently, there is no consensus on the internal nature of depression, the essence of its clinical forms, its outcome, or a strict scientific definition.

The purpose of this work is to present the author's view of the evolutionary nature of depression as a state of nonspecific adaptation is activity, equivalent to suspended animation—to substantiate the clinical forms of depression and its possible outcomes, and to provide a strict scientific definition of depression.

Main provisions: The article presents the author's view on the evolutionary nature of depression, its adaptive character, and provides a strict scientific definition of it. Central and autonomous somatic forms of depression are distinguished, and their clinical characteristics are given. According to the author, the phenomena of depressive depersonalization reflect the phenomena of depressive disintegration of the organism. According to the hypothesis, the outcome of chronic total depression of the organism is its total atrophy; the outcome of chronic central partial depression is atrophy of the central depressive area, as well as diseases of secondary somatic disintegration; the outcome of chronic autonomous somatic depression is atrophy of the somatic depressive area. Senile atrophy of body tissues, according to the author, is the result of chronic total depression during aging.

Conclusion: The evolutionary hypothesis of depression reveals its historical roots and adaptive nature, justifies its scientific definition, clinical forms, and outcome variants, which can be used in scientific and practical activities. Senile atrophy of body tissues is the outcome of chronic depression during aging.

Keywords: depression, evolution, reactivity, adaptation, non-reactivity, disintegration, disintegration diseases, depersonalization, aging, atrophy.

Introduction

The definition of scientific concepts is of great importance for the development of science. Their free interpretation leads away from the essence of the matter. A definition reflects the depth of knowledge of a subject.

The development of science proceeds from one definition to another. Meanwhile, scientific and practical guide-

lines often pay little attention to the definitions of scientific concepts, and the definitions are descriptive and quasi-scientific in nature. For example, the WHO defines depression as a mental disorder whose main symptoms are persistent low mood, loss of interest, low self-esteem, feelings of guilt, and an inability to perform normal tasks.

For example, the WHO defines depression as a mental disorder whose main symptoms are persistent low mood, loss of interest, low self-esteem, feelings of guilt, and an inability to perform normal tasks. Wikipedia: Depression is a mental disorder whose main symptoms are low mood, anhedonia, feelings of melancholy and anxiety, and in severe cases, the depressive triad. In ICD-10, the diagnosis of depression is determined by a long list of typical clinical syndromes, which does not contribute to a scientific definition of the concept.

Currently, there is no consensus on the internal nature of depression [1, 2], the essence of its clinical forms, its outcome, or a strict scientific definition [3, 4]. Some authors associate depression with hypothymia [1, 5, 6], others with a complex affective symptom complex confirmed by path psychological research [7], and still others with biological phases of the organism [8, 9]. Some consider depression to be a psychopathological syndrome, others – a complex neurobiological phenomenon [8, 9, 10]. A number of authors propose more than 18 criteria for depression, which does not clarify its understanding (Hamilton and Beck depression scales).

The neurotransmitter model of depression is simplified [11], revealing its neurohormonal and mediator mechanisms, but it does not reflect its adaptive evolutionary essence. Meanwhile, any psychopathological phenomenon has its phylogenetic roots, historical basis, and is an expression of evolutionary processes, systemic adaptation, driven by natural biological selection, rather than a random consequence of the breakdown or dysfunction of biological structures.

The distinction of neurotic depression appears to be a methodological error due to the confusion of clinical registers [6, 12].

The binary (two-level) concept of depression is relevant, where negative affectivity in the form of alexithymia, anhedonia, dysphoria, anesthesia, and apathy is primary,

Discussion

As an open biological system, the body expresses and maintains itself through the constancy of its internal environment, homeostasis. Homeostasis is regulated at all levels cellular, tissue, and systemic. Homeostasis is the moment of integrity and independence of the organism from the ecosystem, which dictates its morph functional structure through natural selection. The disruption of homeostasis is the essence of destruction and death. The organism, as a single whole, is formed through the reflection of internal needs and the reciprocal initiation of self-regulation processes aimed at satisfying these

axial, reflecting the depth and register of depression, while positive affectivity is secondary, reflecting the reciprocal excitation of central structures adjacent to the focus of depression [13, 14]. In apathetic depression, there is no development of clinical depressive disorders, since apathy is the bottom of depressive register disorders [14]. Apathy is implied by abulia. The clinical picture of apathetic depression resembles the apathetic-abulia syndrome in schizophrenia, but its dynamics are usually reversible and phases in nature. However, the outcome of prolonged central depression may be atrophy of the depressive tissue, symptoms of central function loss, secondary somatic diseases of disintegration, phenomena of depersonalization, dysthymia, and hypochondria [15, 16, 17, 18].

In schizophrenia, the appearance of apathetic syndrome indicates the completion of the pathological process [5, 19, 20]. It is also a bottom-level disorder of the negative register, but it is irreversible, has the character of a neuropsychiatric defect, and has other features. It is also the bottom of negative register disorders, but it is irreversible, has the character of a neuropsychiatric defect, and has other pathogenesis' roots.

Apathetic states are a form of nonspecific adaptation of the organism—are activity. The adaptive significance of these states lies in preventing the disorganization of the organism in pathological conditions [19, 20, 21, 22].

The aim of this article is to use logic, extrapolation, scientific generalization, systematic evolutionary analysis, and theoretical modeling to substantiate an evolutionary model of depression, its scientific definition, internal causes, mechanisms, clinical presentation, and outcome.

The relevance of the article is beyond doubt, as depression is widespread throughout the world and is a frequent cause of disability and mortality among the population [3, 5, 11, 22].

needs, which leads to homeostasis and the preservation of the organism. The disruption of homeostasis is the essence of destruction and death. The organism, as a single whole, is formed through the reflection of internal needs and the reciprocal initiation of self-regulation processes aimed at satisfying these needs, which leads to homeostasis and the preservation of the organism.

Reactivity is the main property of life. Reactivity is the ability of an organism to respond internally to changes in the demands of the ecosystem, a form of interaction with it, a special type of reflection associated with the regulation of homeostasis. A cell is a structural unit of a macro organism, a biological system of the lowest order. Cells are tightly integrated into the macro organism as a single, holistic system and are subject to its requirements, although they have a certain degree of independence, which ensures the plasticity and flexibility of regulation.

The integrative factor regulating the vital functions of a macro organism, as a biological system of the highest order, is reflected need, and the system-forming reactive structure is the basal ganglia of the brain, the emotional centers. In humans, reactivity is differentiated in nature, which is associated with the development of the brain, emotions, higher forms of consciousness, and intellect.

The development of emotions originates from the reflex ring and basal nuclei of homeostasis regulation, which operate on the principle of feedback [23]. Emotions, as a form of consciousness, reflect the body's current needs for substances, energy, and information necessary to maintain homeostasis, and carry the energetic charge of self-regulation and goal setting. Evolutionarily and genetically, emotions are paired with effectors processes in a "stimulus-response" manner and together form a single complex of organism reactivity. Organism reactivity is associated with the energy modules of its vital activity. Emotions are the fundamental center of motivation, goal setting, adaptive reactivity, homeostasis regulation, and systemic integration of the body [20]. As the basic reactive system-forming control center, emotions regulate the movement of energy flows (metabolic, hormonal, and vegetative) within it.

In phylogenetic, under the influence of basic needs, emotions generate the development of the soma as a superhomeostat, the central nervous system, the brain, higher forms of consciousness, and intelligence [20]. Emotions are the center of self-awareness. The ego is a cluster of basic needs and related drives.

Regulation of the body's reactivity range is associated with the regulation of its energy modes of life activity [3,15, 20]. A change in the energy mode of vital activity is a biological adaptation that reflects the plasticity of systemic regulation and allows the body to temporarily change the energy range of its functioning when it needs rest, biological rhythms, or fluctuations in affect [15, 20]. A low adaptive energy regime of vital activity is postulated as depression.

The central mechanisms of regulation of the body's vital activity operate at all its levels cellular, tissue, and systemic but autonomous regulation is also possible. A cell, being a biological system of a lower order, can exhibit the capabilities of autonomous par functional regulation when central regulation is weakened.

Depression is accompanied by suppression of the body's reactivity, and in severe depression, states of total unresponsiveness are observed. Equivalents of depression, like equivalents of other biological phenomena, are projected into the animal world, for nothing arises from nothing, and every biological phenomenon has its own evolutionary history. It is known that primates and other higher mammals suffer from typical clinical variants of depression. In lower animals, states of suspended animation are observed.

According to K. Bernard [24], there are three forms of life, which reflect the stages of development of the reactivity of biological systems in phylogenetic:

1. Latent life (reactivity) - manifests itself only under certain conditions and is completely dependent on the ecosystem. It is observed in spores and bacteria.
2. Oscillating life (reactivity) - a cyclical alternation of life and a state of suspended animation, reflecting natural cycles. Observed in worms, insects, fish, amphibians, reptiles, birds, and some mammals (rodents, badgers, bears).
3. Constant life (reactivity). Does not depend on the ecosystem. Observed in higher mammals and humans.

If we draw physiological parallels, depression is a state of unresponsiveness of the organism, equivalent to suspended animation. Adaptive biological acquisitions in phylogenetic do not disappear, but are appropriated by new, higher achievements of evolution, acquiring a different internal content.

Adaptation can be specific or nonspecific [25]. Non-specific adaptation is associated with ancient non-specific generalized undifferentiated defense mechanisms: hyperthermia, phagocytosis, anabiosis, general adaptation syndrome, stupor, excitement, loss of consciousness, hysteria, autism, trance, pain, and others. The evolution of the living world follows the path of creating specific, differentiated defenses associated with the development of higher forms of neuropsychic activity. However, ancient mechanisms of regulation of the organism do not disappear in the process of evolution, but are appropriated by new mechanisms. When phylogenetically young functions are damaged, they begin to manifest themselves. The dynamics of the body's reactions to damaging factors should not be seen as arbitrary dysfunctions, but as a natural retreat of the body to previous stages of development and the exposure of ancient defense mechanisms. The plasticity of the body's regulation lies in the fact that when the manifestation of new specific functions is impeded, nonspecific relationships come to the fore again. This occurs when the capabilities of specific regulatory systems are impeded under the pressure of extreme ecosystem factors. When there is a functional failure of homeostatic systems and a change in the internal constants of the body's cells, they begin to find themselves in harsh conditions of survival - young, highly organized brain structures responsible for specific adaptation suffer particularly badly. As a result, ancient nonspecific adaptation mechanisms come to the fore.

Ancient nonspecific mechanisms of organism regulation continue to operate at the highest stages of evolution of the living world in the form of their equivalents. Depression is a disease of adaptation.

Anabiosis is a state of unresponsiveness in which the body's vital processes slow down dramatically, helping it survive in conditions that are unfavorable for life [26]; it is a general biological phenomenon that does not disappear even at the highest stages of development of the living world. In some mammals (rodents, bears, badgers), anabiosis is cyclical and seasonal in nature, taking the form of periods of hibernation. As an equivalent, it can manifest itself in humans in the form of seasonal affective disorder.

Depression is a state of unresponsiveness, equivalent to anabiosis, an adaptive suppression of the body's vital processes in order to prevent its systemic disorganization and collapse in pathological conditions. Depression is a form of nonspecific adaptation, reflecting the flexibility of the body's interaction with the ecosystem.

Depressive tissue is tissue in which there is adaptive suppression of vital processes aimed at preserving its structural and functional organization in pathological conditions.

It is known that in the presence of central depression, neuropsychiatric diseases (TBI, encephalitis, ACVA, schizophrenia, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, Pick's disease, etc.) have a benign course, in contrast to lucid states. Depression acts as a factor of biological adaptation [19, 21].

It is likely that somatic diseases also progress benignly in the presence of autonomic somatic depression.

It is advisable to distinguish the following forms of regulation of the body's energy modes of functioning, associated with the regulation of its reactivity threshold.

1. Central forms of regulation of the energy mode of functioning:

a. Cyclical form – ancient generalized, nonspecific, total regulation associated with the basal structures of the brain, reflecting natural cycles and rhythms.

This form of regulation of vital activity is associated with photons of daylight, which affect the total rhythm of the body, including the rhythms of sleep, wakefulness, eating, and libido [22]. Depression is associated with disturbances in the rhythms of the hypothalamic-pituitary, limbic, and pineal systems, which manifests itself in the rhythm of the release of releasing hormones and melatonin.

A low adaptive energy mode of functioning of the body is postulated as total depression, which corresponds to bipolar affective disorder (Table 1).

b. Affective form – more differentiated emotional regulation, dictated by the action of the environment and current needs. The progressive evolution of the body's regulation consists in the development of differentiation of the main emotions. Emotions, reflecting current needs and serving as the basic control center, regulate the energy modes of life activity.

A low adaptive energy mode of functioning of a section of nervous tissue is postulated as central partial depression, which corresponds to recurrent affective disorder (Table 1).

2. Autonomous form of regulation of the energy mode of functioning of somatic tissue. Reflects the known independence of cellular reactions. A low adaptive energy mode of functioning of somatic tissue is postulated as somatic depression.

Table 1. Comparative characteristics of central forms of depression [4, 5, 7, 11, 22, 27]

	Cyclical	Affective
Causes	Heredity, early stress	Involution, chronic stress, co morbid somatic diseases
Phase	+++	+
Start of phase	Autochthonousness	Endoreactivity
Level of depression	Totality	Partiality
Seasonality	+++	+
Circadian rhythm	+++	+
Depth	+++	+++

Age of debut	Young	Average
Phase duration	+	+++
Hypotimia, melancholy	+	+++
Sleep disorders	Hypersomnia	Insomnia
Anesthesia	+++	+
Apathy, sluggishness	+++	+
Alarm	+	+++
Anorexia	+	+++
Decreased libido	+++	+
Premenstrual syndrome	+++	+
Postpartum depression	+++	+
Evening craving for carbohydrates	+++	+
Northern Depression	+++	+
Productive symptoms	+	+++
Reaction to sleep deprivation	+++	+
Photoreaction	+++	+
Resistance to lithium, antidepressants	+	+++
Affectivity	Negative	Positive
Threat of suicide	+	+++
Mixed phases	+	+++
Acceleration of involution		+++
Spontaneous phase break	+++	+
Long-term course	+	+++
Comorbidity	Surfactant abuse, bulimia, migraine	Anxiety, obsessions, PA, anorexia
Premorbid	Cycloidia	Asthenia
The outcome of depression	Intermission	Remission
Nosology	Cyclothymia. BAD	Dysthymia. RAD

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Depression is characterized by systemic disintegration of the body, disruption of its internal unity and integrity of reactions, which manifests itself in symptoms of loss of function in the depressed area, somatoform disorders, and depersonalization phenomena.

Options:

A. Central total depressive disintegration.

The body ceases to function as a single integrated system.

B. Central partial depressive disintegration.

The central depressive focus is switched off from the body's systemic vital activity.

C. Secondary somatic disintegration. The somatic area associated with the central depressive focus does not receive central integrative signals and is disconnected from the organism's systemic vital activity. In this case, the localization of the somatic area of disintegration is an integral part of a complex psychosomatic depressive complex. There are objective indicators of its dysfunction [2].

D. Primary somatic depressive disintegration.

The depressive somatic focus does not respond to central integrative signals and is shut down from systemic life activity.

The following clinical forms of depression can be distinguished:

1. Central depression:

a. Central total depression: clouding of consciousness, apathy, abulia, motor stupor, and mutism, paresis of the senses, fading reflexes, refusal to eat, total depersonalization, hypothermia, analgesia, suppression of basal metabolism, somatic functions, amenorrhea, and others. When coming out of depression, amnesia of its period is observed. Systemic compensatory processes do not occur due to the total disintegration of the body.

b. Central partial depression: the clinical picture is formed from phenomena of depression and loss of function of the central depressive area, negative and positive affectivity, secondary somatoform disorder, and depersonalization. Reciprocal excitation of central functions reflects systemic compensatory processes.

2. Autonomous somatic depression: the clinical picture is formed from primary somatoform disorder, phenomena of somatic depersonalization, hypochondria, dysthymia, and systemic compensatory processes. It rarely comes to the attention of psychiatrists; patients are observed by internists [7].

Partial depressive processes can lead to cascading depressive processes, resulting in total depression and total disintegration of the organism.

Depression is a form of ancient nonspecific adaptation. When treating depression with antidepressants, we expose the pathological process provoke its chronicity, and the formation of a neuropsychiatric defect. Antidepressants should be prescribed strictly according to indications [28].

In the development of chronic (prolonged) depression, it is useful to distinguish between stages of depression, loss of function, and tissue atrophy due to inactivity. Atrophy of depressive tissue is the outcome of chronic depression [16, 17, 18].

The following outcomes in the development of chronic depression can be identified:

A. Total atrophy of body tissues. Occurs in cases of chronic total depression of the organism. Senile tissue atrophy is associated with its chronic total depressive state [29]. With disharmonious aging of the body, atrophic processes in it proceed partially and unevenly.

B. Atrophy of the central depressive area. Occurs in chronic central partial depression.

C. Diseases of secondary somatic disintegration of the body. These are the result of chronic central partial depression. In the secondary somatic focus of disintegration, autonomous par functional processes appear:

1. Atherosclerosis, metabolic disorders.

2. Oncological diseases.

3. Hormonal dysfunctions: type 2 diabetes mellitus, hypothyroidism [2, 30], cachexia, obesity [2].

4. Skin diseases: psoriasis, neurodermatitis [31].

5. Immunodeficiency states.

6. Secondary depression of somatic tissue leading to atrophy.

G. Atrophy of the autonomic somatic depressive area. Occurs with chronic autonomic somatic depression.

Summary

1. Ancient nonspecific adaptive forms of regulation of the body's vital functions in the process of phylogenetic do not disappear, but are appropriated by new, higher forms of regulation, acquiring a different internal content. Depression is a universal protective biological phenomenon, equivalent to suspended animation, a state of unresponsiveness reflecting the body's transition to a low adaptive energy mode of life. Depression is a disease of adaptation.

2. Depressive tissue is tissue in which there is adaptive suppression of vital processes aimed at preserving its structural and functional organization in pathological conditions.

3. Cyclical and affective forms of central regulation of the energy regime of vital activity and an autonomous somatic form of regulation can be distinguished. A low adaptive energy regime of tissue functioning is postulated as depression.

4. In the development of chronic depression, it is useful to distinguish between stages of depression, loss of function, and tissue atrophy due to inactivity. Atrophy of depressive tissue is the outcome of chronic depression.

5. The outcome of chronic total depression is total atrophy of the body. The outcome of chronic central partial depression is atrophy of the depressed area of nervous tissue and secondary somatic disintegration diseases. The outcome of chronic autonomic somatic depression is atrophy of the depressed somatic area.

6. The essence of aging is a chronic total depressive

state of the body, resulting in total tissue atrophy, multiple organ failure, and cachexia. With disharmonious aging of the body, atrophic processes occur partially and unevenly.

7. The phenomena of depressive depersonalization reflect the phenomena of systemic disintegration, as the depressive tissue falls out of the systemic life activity of the body.

8. Reciprocal excitation of central functions in central depression reflects systemic compensatory processes in the body.

9. Antidepressants should be prescribed strictly according to indications due to the adaptability of depression.

10. Approaching humans as the pinnacle of evolution, having absorbed all the historical experience of survival in the process of harsh natural selection, can improve the quality of treatment and prevention programs.

Conclusion

The evolutionary hypothesis of depressive disorders reveals the historical roots of depression, its adaptive nature, and substantiates its scientific definition, clinical forms, and outcome variants, which is of great importance in scientific and practical activities. Senile atrophy of body tissues is the outcome of chronic depression during aging.

It should be emphasized that further scientific research is needed in the field of depressive disorders.

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